

As Discussed the Editorial Letter

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Editors Note

"Dear Readers,

As we read through the volume 1 Issue 1. The Journal of Gastrointestinal Cancer and Stromal Tumors has delved into to make an open access comprehensive forum for GI tumors related academic and clinical publications.

The authors Sanjay Marwah and his team's presentation on spontaneous small bowel perforation following administration of 5-Fluorouracil, Epirubicin and Cyclophosphamide showed unusual complications of chemotherapy. The small bowel perforations are not uncommon in GI Surgical Emergency. But the cause and location were very unique. We hope someone can help us shed more light on the matter. The other case report by Shusuke Sauraba on the treatment of Rectal MALTomas showed an uncommon location of the tumor

following the behavior of its more common cousin the Gastric MALTomas.

The authors Hidefumi Shoshita study on using Supra Pancreatic Lymph nodes as an independent prognostic marker revealed a very unique but understandable result. Multiple of such metastatic lymph nodes had poorer outcomes than just a single positive lymph node.

Abrar Ahmed showed very succinctly how decreased expression of claudins – the adherent proteins were significantly involved in more aggressive tumor pathology and poorer clinical outcomes. Nihat Dilsiz's work on miRNAs in Colorectal Cancer added on to the literature the multi-omics is more effective than standard genomics study. This hopefully helps subcategorize these cancers, with better modalities of treatments and better prognostications."